

1 **GREB1 is the central mediator of resistance to endocrine therapy and cooperates with nuclear**
2 **receptors in effecting this resistance.**

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7 We used a cell culture model of acquired resistance to endocrine therapy (hormone deprivation) to
8 identify genes that cooperated with changes in GREB1 during resistance to cancer therapy in patients with
9 HR+ breast cancer using a clonal system wherein hormone receptor positive MCF7 breast cancer cells
10 were cultured in the presence of tamoxifen until resistance developed and then selected clonally. We
11 identified protein interactions of GREB1 at the systems level using proteomic techniques, identifying ESR1
12 as an interaction partner of GREB1. We integrated these methods, combining proteomic study of GREB1
13 protein-protein interaction partners with whole transcriptome study of acquired resistance to hormone
14 deprivation by endocrine therapy agents in a human cell culture based system to identify nuclear factors
15 that cooperated with GREB1 and ESR1 in resistance to endocrine therapy. In addition, we present
16 evidence demonstrating that mutation of ESR1 or its gene fusion (both of which are found in HR+ patients
17 with resistant disease or during disease relapse) result in induction of GREB1 in the absence of estrogen.
18 GREB1 is among the central mediators (if not the central mediator) of resistance to endocrine therapy and
19 cooperates with nuclear receptors in effecting this biologic process (resistance).
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Results

Experimental Data

I. Identification of nuclear factors that cooperate with GREB1 and ESR1 in resistance to endocrine therapy in humans with hormone receptor positive breast cancer.

We used a cell culture model of acquired resistance to endocrine therapy (hormone deprivation) to identify genes that cooperated with changes in GREB1 during resistance to cancer therapy in patients with HR+ breast cancer using a clonal system wherein hormone receptor positive MCF7 breast cancer cells were cultured in the presence of tamoxifen until resistance developed and then selected clonally.

We measured total transcription in tamoxifen sensitive and tamoxifen resistant clones to identify nuclear factors that cooperated with, or functioned in place of (or perhaps both) GREB1.

We identified protein interactions of GREB1 at the systems level using proteomic techniques and identified ESR1 as an interaction partner of GREB1. We previously demonstrated GREB1 expression was estrogen-responsive, and that its expression was most completely reduced following treatment with letrozole versus tamoxifen in vivo, but that its increased expression was among the genes whose expression, across the transcriptome and identified blindly, was most significantly correlated with residual disease (as compared to complete response), indicating that increases in GREB1 expression were probably required for effective transformation, that GREB1 expression was likely reduced partially or completely following endocrine therapy with either tamoxifen or letrozole but that GREB1 reduction was most effective in patients treated with letrozole, but that GREB1 expression likely increased at some point in most or a subset of HR+ patients that developed resistance to endocrine therapy. This indicated that a GREB1/ESR1 nuclear complex likely existed in variant forms throughout disease progression in humans with breast cancer, first containing both GREB1 and ESR1, later without GREB1 during effective control with endocrine therapy, but then supporting disease recurrence or resistance to ongoing therapy with ESR1 with unidentified nuclear factors.

We combined here proteomic study of GREB1 protein-protein interaction partners with whole transcriptome study of acquired resistance to hormone deprivation by endocrine therapy agents in a human cell culture based system to identify nuclear factors that cooperated with GREB1 and ESR1 in resistance to endocrine therapy.

GSE241654

NR2F2, **NR1D2**, **NR3C1**, **NCOA1**, (decreased) **NRIP1**, NR2C1, **NCOA2**, NR2D2, NR2F1, (decreased) **NR5A2**, NR3C2, and **NCOA5** were

II. ESR1 mutants expressed in patients with breast cancer activated GREB1 expression in breast cancer cells in vitro in the absence of estrogen.

III. ESR1 fusions found in the tumors of patients with breast cancer activate GREB1 expression in xenograft models in vivo.

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2 We next measured total transcription in the tumors of four separate patient cohorts, each consisting
3 of hormone positive receptor breast cancer patients whose treatment response or disease outcome had
4 been identified as a complete response, having residual disease, having a partial response, with stable
5 disease, or having disease progression. We used this data to measure tumor gene expression at the
6 transcriptome level and blindly identify genes whose increased expression was correlated with superior or
inferior clinical outcome. We hypothesized this method would allow us to identify nuclear factors that had
become activated during relapse or resistance to endocrine therapy and cooperated with GREB1 and/or
ESR1 in resistance in hormone positive breast cancer.

7 **Clinical Data (Translational)**

8 Letrozole resistance: GSE146911

9 GSE48905: In a cohort of patients treated with endocrine therapy (fulvestrant) for HR+ breast cancer,
10 increased expression of NRIP1, NFIL3, NCOA7, NCOA1, NCOA2, NR3C1, NR4A3 and NR1H3 were
11 significantly correlated inferior treatment outcome (tumor transcriptomes of patients were measured and
12 compared based on treatment response: partial response, stable disease, or disease progression).

13 GSE33658:

14 In a group of patients treated with endocrine therapy for hormone receptor positive breast cancer
(anastrozole and fulvestrant), increased expression of NCOA5, NCOA1, and NCOA3 was associated with
15 treatment failure (disease progression).

16 We identified NCOA3 here as a GREB1 binding partner using protein-protein interaction using proteomic
17 techniques.

18 GSE25055:

19 In HR+ patients treated with endocrine therapy (mixed luminal A and luminal B subtype), residual disease
(RD) was associated with activation of NR2A1, NR4A3, NR3C1, NCOA2, NR1H3, NR1D2 and to a lesser
20 extent, NCOA1.

21 GSE198650:

22 In HR+ patients treated with endocrine therapy, NCOA2 and NCOA3 were activated in patients with
23 disease progression (PD). NR6A1 was activated in the tumors of patients with disease progression, as
24 was NR5A2 and NRIP1, but to a lesser extent. The expression of NCOA2/3, NR6A1, NR5A2 and NRIP1
was correlated with a specific clinical outcome, treatment failure in hormone positive patients treated with
endocrine therapy, and was identified blindly (transcriptome-level).

25 We identified NR5A2 and NCOA3 here as GREB1 binding partners using protein-protein interaction using
26 proteomic techniques (above).

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Discussion

We describe here the identification of a network of nuclear receptors that function in resistance to endocrine therapy, identified through an integrated systems biologic approach which employed both transcriptomic data from multiple clinical cohorts of humans with hormone positive breast cancer and proteomic methods that identified GREB1-interaction partners at the protein level. Mechanistic studies that studied the molecular consequence of expression of ESR1 fusion proteins and ESR1 point mutations found in humans with hormone receptor positive (luminal A and luminal B) breast cancer supported the notion that despite the complex relationship between GREB1 induction and repression during breast development, transformation of the breast, response to endocrine therapy agents in humans with HR+ breast cancer and relapse/resistance in humans with HR+ breast cancer, induction rather than repression of GREB1 was associated with disease resistance.